

Methodology of the climate suitability analysis of *Amyelois transitella*

Caterina Campese, Diego Guidotti, Eugenio Rossi, Giuseppe Stancanelli, Andrea Maiorano

Note on this report

This document includes a description of the climate suitability analysis methodology applied to *Amyelois transitella*. The analysis was conducted in the context of the *EFSA Pest risk assessment of Amyelois transitella for the European Union* (EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH) et al., 2022). The related PRA contains the results and discussion of the analysis.

Observed distribution Data

Literature search about *Amyelois transitella* global distribution (Campese et al., 2022) allowed the extraction of 144 records¹ of the presence of *Amyelois transitella* (Observation table, ANNEX B) including sixteen points which were eventually excluded from the distribution maps due to little resolution or little and unclear information associated. Out of these records, 97 were punctual observation reporting specific coordinates, or small administrative units (e.g.: cities or counties) that were indicated using the coordinates given by Google Earth (online version, available at: <https://earth.google.com/web>). Forty-seven records were related to larger administrative units like Regions. *Amyelois transitella* was observed from the southern US states (Figure 1) to Northern Argentina. Observation from Washington State reported by EPPO (DROPSA, 2016) was excluded from the map due to uncertainty on the persistence of the pest presence in the State and lack of other scientific literature confirming the presence. All the observations collected for Europe (Austria: Burmann et al 1995; Essl et al 2002; Germany: DROPSA, 2016; Italy: Trematerra 1988; Netherlands: Huisman et al 2003), for Japan and South Korea (Japan: Sonda 1962, Trematerra 1988, Hong, 2012; South Korea: Hong, 2012) were found to be interceptions (DROPSA, 2016, Hong, 2012) and therefore excluded. The observations from Georgetown, Guyana and Santo Domingo, Dominican Republic (Heinrich, 1956) refer to specimens from Museums, therefore they were considered uncertain observations and not included in the map. Canada (DROPSA, 2016) and Uruguay (Burks, 2015) were excluded from the map, due to the lack of more precise information and considering that possible observations of *A. transitella* in these countries could be transient. An observation point collected in South Africa, Green Valley Nuts (Grobel, 2010) was not considered, due to the lack of precise information on species identification. Scattered information were found in the literature reporting *A. transitella* presence in Argentina (EPPO Minidatsheet 2016; Legner 1982, 1983). Legner (1982, 1983) reported the pest as present “throughout Uruguay and central Argentina to 35° S. lat., and across the continent to the eastern slopes of the Andes” (Legner, 1983), “where climatic similarities with California’s Central Valley are great” (Legner, 1982).

¹ As a general methodological rule, information at regional or county level or location with specific coordinates are preferred to lower resolution information (e.g.: Country level). Therefore, when different levels of information were present for a given area, the most precise ones were considered, e.g: having both California (Country level) and Butte County as observations, only Butte County was mapped.

Figure 1. Observed distribution of *Amyelois transitella* in the Americas. Figure A shows only observations at different administrative levels (highlighted in red). Figure B shows only punctual observations (with geographic coordinates) of the pest (red dots).

Methods

Climate Classification analysis

Based on the Köppen–Geiger climate classification approach (SCAN-Clim tool, EFSA and Maiorano, A., 2022), the climate types present in the location of observations of *A. transitella* were identified and mapped. Since the area of the assessment is the EU, the output maps considered only climate types that are also present in this area.

CLIMEX analysis

Climate suitability was analysed using the CLIMEX model (Kriticos et al. 2015). The model was run using the climate dataset available in CLIMEX, CM30 1995H V2 WO (www.climond.org), package v4.1. This dataset is based on the 0.5° world grid of historical meteorological data (30 years centered on 1995), from the Climate Research Unit (Norwich, UK), transformed using the methods of Kriticos et al., 2012. Parameter values were fixed according to information found in the literature or adjusted iteratively (Cold stress, Heat stress and Dry stress accumulation rates) until the simulated climate suitability was consistent with the observed distribution (Figure 1). For illustrative purposes, Figure 2 shows the relations among growth and stress temperature parameters, used to model *A. transitella* potential distribution (note that temperature values are not proportionally scaled on the axis).

Table 1. CLIMEX Parameter Values for *Amyelois transitella**. CLIMEX parameter file for *A. transitella* is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6696522>.

Parameters	Description	Value	Sources
Temperature			
DV0	Lower temperature threshold	12.8 °C	EFSA, 2021; Engle et al., 1983; Hamby et al., 2013; Holtz et al., 2002; Kuenen et al., 2010; Zalom et al., 1998; Seaman et al., 1984; Sanderson et al., 1986; Sanderson et al., 1989.
DV1	Lower optimal temperature	24°C	Agudelo et al., 2014; Gal, 1978.
DV2	Upper optimal temperature	32 °C	Falcon, 1965; Sanderson et al., 1989.
DV3	Upper temperature threshold	37.8 °C	Falcon, 1965; Sanderson et al., 1989.
Cold stress			
TTCS	Cold stress temperature threshold	0°C	Johnson, 2007; Tebbets et al., 1978
THCS	Cold stress accumulation rate	-0.001 week-1	Adjusted iteratively
Heat stress			
TTHS	Heat stress temperature threshold	36.7 °C	Falcon, 1965; Sanderson et al., 1989
THHS	Heat stress accumulation rate	0.05 week-1	Adjusted iteratively
Dry stress			
HDS	Dry stress accumulation rate	-0.001 week-1	Adjusted iteratively
PDD	Minimum degree day sum needed to complete a generation	417.5° C days	Seaman et al., 1984; Sanderson et al., 1989

(*) Default 'CLIMEX temperate template' parameters values were used for the following parameters: DTCS, DHCS, TTCSA, THCSA (Cold stress); DTHS, DHHS (Heat stress); SMDS (Dry stress).

Figure 2. CLIMEX, temperature parameters for growth (green), cold stress (blue), and heat stress (red). The figure is for illustrative purposes, hence scale and slopes are representative.

Potential number of generations during the growing season

The potential number of generations during the growing season was estimated using a degree-day model based on a base temperature for development of 12.8°C. Weather data were from the Copernicus Climate Change Service information². Degree-day calculation was based on hourly temperature data from the ERA5-Land dataset (Muñoz Sabater, 2019). For each pixel of the ERA5-Land 9 km (0.08°) regular grid, degree-days were calculated for each year from 1991-2020 and then averaged.

Content of the *Amyelois transitella* Zenodo repository

[Amyelois_transitella_ExtensiveLitSearch.pdf](#)

The file contains the methodology and results of the Extensive Literature Research for *Amyelois transitella*. Here the results of the databases interrogations are presented together with the process applied for documents screening and selection, summarised by a PRISMA diagram. Tables show the logic behind data extraction from the selected documents.

[Amyelois_transitella_ClimateSuitability_Report.pdf](#)

The file contains the methodology of the Climate Suitability Analysis for *Amyelois transitella*. Here the data used are contextualised, and the methodology of the Climate Classification Analysis, CLIMEX simulation, and potential development are reported.

[Amyelois_transitella_ANNEX_A_Master_file.xlsx](#)

The file contains the list of documents selected for data extraction. The description of the fields can be found in [Amyelois_transitella_ExtensiveLitSearch.pdf](#).

[Amyelois_transitella_ANNEX_B_Observations.csv](#)

The file contains the list of extracted observation points, both precise locations and administrative units. The description of the fields can be found in [Amyelois_transitella_ExtensiveLitSearch.pdf](#).

Maps in .jpeg format

Maps of CLIMEX model simulations:

- [Amyelois_transitella_CLIMEX_ColdStress_stand-alone.jpeg](#)
- [Amyelois_transitella_CLIMEX_EI_Stand-alone.jpeg](#)

Maps of Climate Classification Analysis:

- [Amyelois_transitella_KG_full_stand-alone.jpeg](#)
- [Amyelois_transitella_KG_noCfb_stand-alone.jpeg](#)
- [Amyelois_transitella_obs_stand-alone.jpeg](#)

[Amyelois_transitella_PRA.gpkg](#)

This is a GeoPackage (.gpkg) file containing the GIS layers of the results of the analysis.

[Amyelois_transitella_qgis_styles.zip](#)

The folder contains the QGIS styles to replicate the simbologies used in the maps published in the PRA. These styles were applied to the layers contained in [Amyelois_transitella_PRA.gpkg](#).

² Neither the European Commission nor ECMWF is responsible for any use that may be made of the Copernicus Information or Data it contains

[Amyelois_transitella_CLIMEX_parameters.cxp](#)

The file contains the parameterization used to run the simulations in the CLIMEX model.

References

- Agudelo DCM, Rueda GD and Yepes F, 2014. Primer Registro De *Amyelois transitella* (Walker) En El Fruto Del Tamarindo: El Caso De Santa Fe De Antioquia. Revista Científica Sabia, 1:6-12.
- Burks, Charles S.,Yasin, Muhammad,El-Shafie, Hamadttu A. F.,Wakil, Waqasm, 2015. Pests of Stored Dates. Sustainable Pest Management in Date Palm: Current Status and Emerging Challenges.
- Burmann, K., 1986, Beiträge zur Microlepidopteren-Fauna Tirols. IX. Pterophoridae (Insecta: Lepidoptera). – Berichte des naturwissenschaftlichen-medizinischen Verein Innsbruck – 73: 133 – 146. Available online: https://www.zobodat.at/pdf/BERI_73_0133-0146.pdf.
- Campese C., Muñoz Guajardo I., Da Costa I., Stancanelli G., Maiorano A., 2022. Extensive literature research for *Amyelois transitella* global distribution and eco-physiological parameters. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6696522>
- DROPSA, 2016. Minidatasheet on *Amyelois transitella* available in pdf on EPPO website. Available online: <https://gd.eppo.int/taxon/PARMTR/documents>.
- EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH), et al., 2021. Scientific Opinion on the pest categorisation of *Amyelois transitella*. EFSA Journal 2021;19(6):6666, 27 pp: <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2021.6666>.
- EFSA Panel on Plant Health (PLH), et al., 2022. Pest risk assessment of *Amyelois transitella* for the European Union, EFSA Journal, <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2022.7523>
- Engle CE and Barnes MM, 1983. Developmental threshold temperature and heat unit accumulation required for egg hatch of navel orangeworm (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae). Environmental Entomology, 12, 1215–1217.
- ESSL, F. & RABITSCH, W., 2002, Neobiota in Österreich. Umweltbundesamt, Wien, 432 pp. Available online: <https://www.umweltbundesamt.at/fileadmin/site/publikationen/dp089z.pdf>.
- Falcon LA, 1965. Factors affecting field populations of the navel orange worm, *Paramyelois transitella* (Walker), on walnuts in northern California Coleoptera, Hymenoptera, Predator. Dbs Abstr, 25:3772-3772.
- Gal A, 1978. Der Einfluss der Temperatur auf die Fruchtbarkeit, Entwicklungs-und Überlebensrate von *Paramyelois transitella* (Lep., Pyralidae). Mitteilungen der Deutschen Gesellschaft fuer Allgemeine und Angewandte Entomologie, 1:265-269.
- Grobler A, 2010. Survival of the navel orangeworm, *Amyelois transitella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), on pistachio in South Africa. University of the Free State.
- Hamby KA and Zalom FG, 2013. Relationship of Almond Kernel Damage Occurrence to Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) Success. Journal of economic entomology, 106:1365-1372. doi: 10.1603/ec12473.
- Heinrich, C., 1956, American moths of the subfamily Phycitinae. Washington US Nat Mus Bull. Volume: VIII + 581 pp.-VIII + 581 pp.
- Holtz BA, 2002. Plant protection for pistachio. Horttechnology, 12:626-632. doi: 10.21273/horttech.12.4.626.

- Hong K-J, Hong S, Ryu C and Lee Y, 2012. Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) Intercepted on Fresh Oranges from the USA at the Korean Port of Entry. *Korean Journal of Applied Entomology*, 51:295-297. doi: 10.5656/ksae.2012.06.0.020.
- Huisman KJ, Koster JC, van Nieukerken EJ and Ulenberg SA, 2003. Microlepidoptera in The Netherlands in 2000. *Entomologische Berichten (Amsterdam)*, 63:88-102.
- Johnson JA, 2007. Survival of Indianmeal moth and navel orangeworm (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) at low temperatures. *Journal of economic entomology*, 100:1482-1488. doi: 10.1093/jee/100.4.1482
- Kriticos, D.J., Webber, B.L., Leriche, A., Ota, N., Macadam, I., Bathols, J. and Scott, J.K. 2012. CliMond: global high resolution historical and future scenario climate surfaces for bioclimatic modelling. *Methods in Ecology and Evolution*. 3:53-64
- Kriticos, D.J., Maywald, G.F., Yonow, T., Zurcher, E.J., Herrmann, N.I. and Sutherst, R.W. 2015. CLIMEX Version 4: Exploring the effects of climate on plants, animals and diseases. Canberra: CSIRO.
- Kuenen LPS and Siegel JP, 2010. Protracted Emergence of Overwintering *Amyelois transitella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) From Pistachios and Almonds in California. *Environmental Entomology*, 39:1059-1067. doi: 10.1603/en09277.
- Landolt PJ and Curtis CE, 1982. Effects Of Temperature On The Circadian-Rhythm Of Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae) Sexual-Activity. *Environmental Entomology*, 11:107-110. doi: 10.1093/ee/11.1.107.
- Legner EF, Gordh G, Silveira-Guido A and Badgley ME, 1982. New wasp may help control navel orangeworm. *California Agriculture*, 36:4-5.
- Legner EF, 1983. Patterns Of Field Diapause In The Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera, Phycitidae) And 3 Imported Parasites *Amyelois Transitella* (Walker). *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 76:503-506. doi: 10.1093/aesa/76.3.503.
- Muñoz-Sabater J, Dutra E, Agustí-Panareda A, Albergel C, Arduini G, Balsamo G, Boussetta S, Choulga M, Harrigan S, Hersbach H, Martens B, Miralles DG, Piles M, Rodríguez-Fernández NJ, Zsoter E, Buontempo C and Thépaut JN, 2021. ERA5-Land: a state-of-the-art global reanalysis dataset for land applications. *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 13:4349-4383. doi: 10.5194/essd-13-4349-2021.
- Rice RE, Sadler LL, Hoffmann ML and Jones RA, 1976. Egg Traps For Navel Orangeworm, *Paramyelois-Transitella* (Walker) Lepidoptera-Pyralidae. *Environmental Entomology*, 5:697-701. doi: 10.1093/ee/5.4.697.
- Sanderson JP, 1986. Synthesis of a thermal summation model for the development of the navel orangeworm on almonds in California. *Dissertation Abstracts International B Sciences and Engineering*, 47:1401-1401.
- Sanderson JP, Barnes MM, Youngman RR and Engle CE, 1989. Developmental Rates Of The Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae) At Various Constant Temperatures. *Journal of economic entomology*, 82:1096-1100. doi: 10.1093/jee/82.4.1096.
- Sanderson JP, Barnes MM and Seaman WS, 1989. Synthesis and validation of a degree-day model for navel orangeworm (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae) development in california almond orchards. *Environmental Entomology*, 18:612-617. doi: 10.1093/ee/18.4.612.

Seaman WS and Barnes MM, 1984. Thermal Summation For The Development Of The Navel Orangeworm In Almond (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae). *Environmental Entomology*, 13:81-85. doi: 10.1093/ee/13.1.81.

Siegel JP and Kuenen LPSB, 2011. Variable Developmental Rate and Survival of Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) on Pistachio. *Journal of economic entomology*, 104:532-539. doi: 10.1603/ec10177.

Sonda M, 1962. An interception of the navel-orange worm, *Paramyelois transitella* (Walker), attacking English walnuts from California (Lepidoptera, Pyralidae). *Kontyu*, 30:282-283.

Tebbets JS, Curtis CE and Fries RD, 1978. Mortality Of Immature Stages Of The Navel Orangeworm (Lepidoptera-Pyralidae) Stored At 3.5-Degrees-C. *Journal of economic entomology*, 71:875-876. doi: 10.1093/jee/71.6.875.

Trematerra P, 1988. *Paramyelois transitella* (Walker) lepidottero americano presente nelle noci importate dalla California. *Informatore Fitopatologico*, 38, 51-55.

Zalom FG, Connell JH and Bentley WJ, 1998. Validation of phenology models for predicting development of the navel orangeworm *Ameylois transitella* (Walker) in California almond orchards. In: Ferguson L and Kester D (eds.). *Second International Symposium on Pistachios and Almonds*. pp. 525-533.

Appendix

Figure 3. Köppen–Geiger climate types that are present in Europe and have also been associated with detection of *Amyelois transitella*.

Figure 4. Köppen–Geiger climate types that are present in Europe and have also been associated with detections of *Amyelois transitella*. In this figure the climate type Cfb (temperate oceanic) was removed as there is uncertainty on the suitability of this climate type for establishment of *A. transitella* (EFSA Panel on Plant Health et al., 2022)

Figure 5. CLIMEX Ecoclimatic Index (EI) for *Amyelois transitella* interpolated across the World. The EI characterise the climatic suitability of areas to support a species persistence on a scale from 0 (unsuitability) to 100 (high suitability for persistence). Red dots indicate punctual observations of the pest.

Figure 6: CLIMEX Cold Stress for *Amyelois transitella*. Red dots indicate punctual observations of the pest. Legend shows the Cold Stress Index (EI), a darker colour corresponds to a higher stress condition. Zero degree (Johnson, 2007; Tebbets et al., 1978) was used as cold stress temperature threshold with an accumulation rate of -0.001 week^{-1} .